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“All that I Am Craving Is the Talk”: Collaboration, Translation and Lady Gregory’s *Workhouse Ward*

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ABSTRACT

Central to the collaborative dynamics of the Irish Revival, Lady Gregory had a particularly fruitful working relationship with Douglas Hyde (Dubhghlas de hÍde), whose plays she translated and, in many instances, co-authored. This article takes as its case study Gregory’s 1908 play *The Workhouse Ward*, which arose out of a dramatic scenario she provided to Hyde as the basis for his *Teach na mBocht* (1903) – translated by Gregory as *The Poorhouse* (1903). By studying Gregory’s scenarios and draft translations alongside the various published versions, the article responds to Héléne Buzelin’s call for a “process-oriented kind of research” into translation practice. Through this genetic approach, the article allows us to better understand how language and gender politics shaped key plays of the Irish national theatre movement and argues that future editions of Gregory’s and Hyde’s works should include all plays in which each author had significant creative input.

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On 6 January 1899, a Punch-and-Judy show was staged at Lady Gregory’s Coole Park for the children of nearby Gort Workhouse.¹ It was Gregory’s custom to invite the workhouse children to her estate each Christmas, where they would receive gifts and be entertained. On this occasion, the entertainers were Gaelic League president Douglas Hyde and Norma Borthwick, a member of the League’s executive council. In Gregory’s account, Hyde and Borthwick’s performance “brought down the house”:

Dr. H. chastising the baby much applauded, the children had probably themselves been chastised in the same words! He made the “pilér” [policeman] speak in English, & then abused him in Irish, & said the paisdin [baby] had fallen out of the window by himself! A success on the whole but very tiring²

What is notable about Gregory’s description is her emphasis on the show’s bilingualism, with its comic effect depending on audience awareness of the different statuses of the two

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¹Dating based on *Lady Gregory’s Diaries*, 198–201. Though most commentators follow Gregory herself in dating the show to December 1898, the diaries indicate it having taken place on the first Friday of 1899 (i.e., 6 January). See Gregory, *Poets and Dreamers*, 2nd ed., 196.

²*Lady Gregory’s Diaries*, 200.

languages. While “the talk” is a key aspect of the play I will analyse below, the language in which this talk took place was a live political issue on the island at the turn of the century. How did these language dynamics shape the collaborative forces behind the national theatre movement in turn-of-the-century Ireland? This article takes as its case study one bilingual theatre collaboration, Gregory and Hyde’s *Teach na mBocht / The Poorhouse*, later adapted as *The Workhouse Ward*, examining under-regarded authorial drafts to help us understand the highly political dynamics of “the talk”, both on- and offstage, in the Irish national theatre movement.

When Hyde and Borthwick’s Punch-and-Judy show was staged, Ireland’s linguistic makeup was in a state of flux, and the Gaelic League (founded 1893) was soon to become a central force in reviving the use of Irish through educational reform, language classes and theatrical performance.³ The day before Hyde and Borthwick’s show, a branch of the League had been established in Kiltartan, launched by the local parish priest, Fr Fahey: “he made a speech in Irish, with a very English accent & condescending manner”, wrote Gregory in her diary, hinting at the tensions in her relationship with the Catholic clergy. Fahey was followed by her close friend:

Dr. Hyde made a very eloquent speech in Irish, not that I cd understand it, but it roused the people – then he made one in English in which he drew attention to the inferiority of the vocabulary of the English peasant to that of the Irish – all very good except that he came a little too near what may be taken for politics in saying “Let the English go their road & let us go ours – & God forbid their road should ever be our road” – A branch of the League was formed, & Miss B[orthwick]. is to start classes⁴

Gregory herself took lessons with Borthwick, and developed a working knowledge of the language that led to her translating works by Hyde and others, in turn forming a key element of her own “bilingual style” when writing in English.⁵ But, as Gregory’s private reaction to Hyde’s Kiltartan speech demonstrates, there were also tensions inherent in their relationship, which would come to the fore in more wide-ranging controversies triggered by the plays of Gregory’s close colleague J. M. Synge.⁶ By inviting the Gaelic League into Coole Park in order to entertain the local workhouse children through stage performance, Gregory brought together three institutions – the language movement, the national theatre movement and the workhouse – which constituted the network of her own collaboration with Hyde through translation. In hosting such gatherings, Gregory made of her home not just a backstage arena in which writers gathered to prepare their plays but a veritable performance space in which the drama

³In the 1891 census, 680,174 people were recorded as being Irish speakers (14.5 percent of the total population), while the figure recorded of those who spoke Irish only was 38,121 (0.8 percent of the total population), down from 319,602 in 1851. Hindley, *Death of the Irish Language*, 19.

⁴*Lady Gregory’s Diaries*, 199–200. Square brackets in *Lady Gregory’s Diaries*.

⁵The term is used by Declan Kiberd to refer to the work of J. M. Synge – it also applies to Gregory’s writing. Kiberd, *Synge and the Irish Language*, 5–6; 196–215.

⁶In 1903, Hyde left the Irish National Theatre Society – which had recently staged Gregory’s first play – in protest at their production of Synge’s *In the Shadow of the Glen*. Hogan and Kilroy, *Laying the Foundations*, 75; Kelly, *Yeats Chronology*, 88. In 1911, Hyde publicly repudiated any connection between the Gaelic League and the Abbey Theatre, now co-directed by Gregory and W. B. Yeats, in response to pressure from key fundraisers, who were angry at Gregory linking the League and the Abbey during a controversial tour of Synge’s *Playboy of the Western World* in the United States. Dunleavy, “Pattern of Three Threads”, 140–1. See also Dunleavy and Dunleavy, *Douglas Hyde*, 319–20.

of the Irish Revival was played out.⁷ As we will see, this drama unfolded at a time of major tensions between different factions and figures in the Revival.

Gregory later claimed that Hyde and Borthwick's puppet show at Coole heralded "the beginning of modern Irish[-language] drama".⁸ However, in spite of this being stated in an introduction to her own translations, she omits herself from the ensuing story, making no mention of her role as translator of ten of Hyde's plays. This reflects a broader pattern in which female writers are often written out of their collaborations with male colleagues,⁹ sometimes by literary critics, sometimes by collaborators themselves. In the above example, Gregory writes herself out of her own story, as she also seems to have done in the better-known case of *Cathleen Ni Houlihan*, one of the many plays she co-authored with W. B. Yeats.¹⁰ That instance of co-authorship was brought to light by James Pethica's manuscript research into the early versions of the play, providing a good example of how gender inequality in the public sphere can be challenged by examining compositional drafts.¹¹ Following this methodological lead, my article takes a genetic approach, tracking Hyde and Gregory's collaboration through the compositional drafts of a co-authored comedy initially published as *Teach na mBocht* alongside Gregory's translation, *The Poorhouse*, in Yeats's periodical *Samhain* (1903), then substantially re-written by Gregory as *The Workhouse Ward* (staged 1908). Since genetic analysis takes into account the temporal aspect of a work's creation over time, it can highlight the use of "different strategies at different moments in the composition of [a] translation".¹² A diachronic analysis of Gregory's translation manuscripts will reveal her growing independence from Hyde and Yeats as she developed her own skills as a playwright.

For Anthony Cordingley and Céline Frigau Manning, "all translation is collaborative", due to translation's inherently social nature.¹³ But some translations are more collaborative than others, going far beyond what is written on the page. My genetic approach to tracking the Gregory-Hyde collaboration is a response to Héléne Buzelin's call for a "process-oriented kind of research" into translation practice, analysing the genesis of translations as part of their evolution within a broader network.¹⁴ Building on Bruno Latour's

⁷Though there is not sufficient room in this article to fully explore Coole Park's status as a performance space, it is notable that many revivalist accounts of life there revolve around the testing out of new works on a select audience, usually through private readings, as well as cultural performances of a broader variety, such as the signatures left by visitors on the famous Autograph Tree. Similarly, a full analysis of the engagement of inmates from Gort Workhouse in Gaelic League activity is an important topic that requires further research.

⁸Gregory, *Poets and Dreamers*, 2nd ed., 196. As Brian Ó Conchubhair notes, "Theatre in Irish, such as it is, began not in Ireland but in the first Steinway Hall on 14th Street, Manhattan, where the New York Society for the Preservation of the Irish Language staged Paul McSwiney's libretto *An Bard 'gus an Fó: A Gaelic Idyll* on Thanksgiving 1884'. Ó Conchubhair, "Twisting in the Wind", 251. Hyde and Borthwick had attended a historical performance entitled *The Passing of Conall* in November 1898. The *Freeman's Journal* reported that one scene of this "play" had been translated into Irish and then "acted both in Irish and English". "Aenach Tírconail – The Great Irish Festival", *Freeman's Journal*, 19 November 1898, 6. For more on earlier dramatic texts in Irish, see O'Leary, "What Would Willie Say?", 159–60 and Ó Siadhail, *Stair Dhrámaíocht na Gaeilge*, 19–21.

⁹London, *Writing Double*, 3–4.

¹⁰For Nicholas Grene, "it seems likely that, apart from the early plays *The Land of Heart's Desire* and *The Countess Cathleen*, Gregory had a hand in every one of Yeats's plays before 1908", showing just how important her input was to his early theatrical oeuvre. Grene, "Lady Gregory", 63.

¹¹See Pethica, "Our Kathleen".

¹²Cordingley and Montini, "Genetic Translation Studies", 4.

¹³Cordingley and Frigau Manning, "What Is Collaborative Translation?", 23. Such concepts were very much in the air during the Revival, with Synge declaring that "All art is a collaboration" in his preface to *The Playboy of the Western World*, a play which itself draws heavily on translation. Synge, *Plays 2*, 53.

¹⁴Buzelin, "Unexpected Allies", 215.

Actor–Network Theory, Buzelin has studied the actor-networks involved in translations carried out for contemporary publishing houses, often done by teams of translators.¹⁵ While the networks involved in the composition of *Teach na mBocht / The Poorhouse / The Workhouse Ward* are quite different in nature, Buzelin’s method can bear fruit here too. Paying close attention to the translation dynamics involved in particular word choices will allow us to fully appreciate the diversity of roles the two writers played within the different networks they occupied: as well as being Hyde’s translator, Gregory was a landowner, patron, folklorist and a key playwright in the early national theatre movement; as well as writing plays in Irish for Gregory’s theatre, Hyde was a translator, folklorist, education activist and a key figure in the language revival movement. These relationships between translation, playwriting and other forms of cultural work will inform my analysis of *Teach na mBocht / The Poorhouse / The Workhouse Ward*. First, I will set the stage by examining some of the other translations Gregory and Hyde were involved in.

Gregory translating Hyde

Despite the centrality of translation to their working relationship, it has never been easy to identify the precise translational dynamics between Hyde and Gregory.¹⁶ Philip O’Leary sums up the situation in scholarship on their work when he writes of Gregory’s “not always easily isolated influence on Hyde’s plays”.¹⁷ Examining Gregory’s preliminary scenarios and translation manuscripts allows us to see that influence at work. In what follows, I briefly examine the translation patterns in two plays published in her *Poets and Dreamers* (1903), *The Marriage* and *The Lost Saint*, which were shaped by the creative network established at Coole Park.¹⁸

“Coole is said to be the workshop of Ireland”, wrote Gregory proudly in 1902.¹⁹ The Coole workshop became a key workplace for writers like Yeats and Hyde,²⁰ with Gregory at the helm, pushing them to get work done. This expectation from his host was clear from the outset of Yeats’s time there:²¹

On his first visit, he later recalled, he did little work – and then discovered that this was a disappointment to his hostess. By the following summer, when he was again at Coole, a routine had been established and [George] Russell [Æ] could write to Gregory: “he ought

¹⁵Latour, *Reassembling the Social*; Buzelin, “Translations ‘in the Making’”, 135–69.

¹⁶Hyde helped Gregory with her translation of the Ulster Cycle of myths, published as *Cuchulain of Muirthemne* (1902), while Gregory was inspired by his translation of Irish folk songs, especially his *Love Songs of Connacht* (1893).

¹⁷O’Leary, “What Would Willie Say?”, 168.

¹⁸The translator’s manuscript of *The Twisting of the Rope* could not be found during my research while *The Tinker and the Sheeog* (*An Tincéar agus an tSídheóg*, 1902) and *The Matchmaking* (*An Cleamhnas*, 1903) were posthumously edited from her translator’s manuscript for inclusion in the 1974 Coole edition of *Poets and Dreamers*. As such, comparisons between the drafts and the published text cannot be relied upon as evidence of Gregory’s translation process. Hyde’s Irish-language titles are unstable across editions; their non-standard spellings sometimes differ even within the one edition. The titles I use are taken from the covers of editions held in UCD Special Collections.

¹⁹Gregory to Wilfrid Scawen Blunt, 30 April 1902, Folder 29, Berg Collection, qtd in Pilz, “Return to the People”, 8.

²⁰Hyde’s biographers mention that “it seemed that his muse resided in what had become ‘his room’ at Coole”, while R. F. Foster talks of Coole as being “the place where he [Yeats] could write poetry”. Dunleavy and Dunleavy, *Douglas Hyde*, 224; Foster, *The Apprentice Mage*, 182.

²¹Yeats had made a short visit in 1896, but this passage relates to his first substantial trip in 1897. Foster, *The Apprentice Mage*, 181, 570n73.

to be locked in his room with a certain amount of work to be done or he ought not to get dinner until he has produced a specified number of lines every day”.²²

In 1901, Gregory would express her own wish to keep Yeats on a short lease: “Lock him up. [...] No work no breakfast”.²³ She continued to be the instigator of writing work at Coole, later to be joined in this role by Yeats himself when they pushed Hyde to compose plays. This gives a good idea of Coole’s workshop atmosphere, where writers came and went under Gregory’s watchful and encouraging stewardship. Hyde and Gregory’s plays arose out of this creative milieu, with Yeats as another key collaborator, the two men spending multiple summer trips together at Coole around the turn of the century.

Yeats and Gregory were keen to have plays staged in Irish, and saw Hyde as the man for this job, so they provided him with material with which he could quickly compose them. *An Pósadh (The Marriage)* was based on a tale told to Gregory about the blind poet Raftery (Antaine Raiftearaí, 1799–1835).²⁴ In the play, he comes to the house of a recently married young couple which contains very few material possessions. Raftery encourages them to welcome members of the local community into their sparsely furnished home, whereupon he proceeds to milk each visitor for gifts. The piece ends with the community realising they have been in the presence of the legendary Raftery, whose day’s earnings he has left to the young couple. A Young Man then reports that he has been at Raftery’s grave – the figure they saw was a ghost. All the principal action is outlined in Gregory’s typescript scenario, entitled “The Wedding”, which contains no direct speech, but does include phrases that ended up in the published dialogue.²⁵ With this in mind, we can see Gregory’s translation of the play as one step in a longer collaborative process, and her status as a co-author as well as a translator.

Gregory’s manuscripts record an increasing distance between Hyde’s texts and her translations. The main trend is for her to move from literal, word-for-word translations to (slightly) freer interpretations, albeit never straying so far that her English versions could not be used as parallel texts to the Irish original, an important aspect in serving the language-learning ambitions of audience members drawn from Hyde’s Gaelic League. For instance, when Martin speaks of “féasta ár bpósta” [the feast of our wedding], Gregory initially translates this as “our wedding feast” before entering the open variant “dinner”, which is what appears in the published text.²⁶ Likewise, when Raftery tells some recently arrived boys to invite others to the wedding, the translation is first a fairly literal rendering of Hyde’s “Abair leo go bhfuil bainis ’s damhsa le bheith annso anocht, ’s go gcaithfidh siad teacht isteach”: “tell them there is a wedding + dance here this evening, + they must come in” (SP 88; MMS 23r). In the published text, Gregory gets rid of the paratactic syntax carried over from the Irish, making the phrase more direct: “tell them they must come in: there is a wedding-dance here this evening” (SP 89; PD 223). Similarly, when Another Boy says of the people, “Ní thiochfaidh siad isteach”, Gregory first drafted the literal “They will not come in”, then opted for a

²²Foster, *The Apprentice Mage*, 182.

²³Ibid., 570n77.

²⁴See Dunleavy and Dunleavy, “Introduction”, 18; Gregory, *Poets and Dreamers*, 2nd ed., 35. Henceforth referenced as PD in the text. Hyde had been carrying out his own research on Raftery when he met Gregory, and this shared interest in the poet was an important basis for their collaborations. See Dunleavy and Dunleavy, *Douglas Hyde*, 204–5.

²⁵Typescript of outline of play, with the author’s ms. corrections, Berg Collection.

²⁶Hyde, *Selected Plays*, 86–7. Henceforth referenced as SP in the text; PD 220; Translator’s manuscript, Berg Collection, 17r. Henceforth referenced as MMS in the text.

more pointed interrogation in the published text: “Why would they come in?” (*SP* 88–9; *MMS* 25r; *PD* 223). In the notebook, the songs Raftery sings too are translated literally, but given a freer translation in the published playtext. While this gradual movement away from direct translation is by no means unheard of as a strategy for translators, I will show that these textual shifts are part of a broader picture whereby Gregory gradually gains authorial independence from Hyde.

This is not to suggest that the power dynamics were all one-way; according to Hyde, Gregory and Yeats literally pushed him to write another play. On 25 August 1902, he recorded (in Irish) in his diary: “They *shoved* me into my room and I wrote a small play in three or four hours on Angus the Culdee”.²⁷ This was *An Naomh ar Iarraidh* (1902; translated as *The Lost Saint*, 1903), and though no scenario exists in Gregory’s or Hyde’s archives at the New York Public Library, she does mention creating one with Yeats in order to structure the drama. Gregory’s same diary entry mentions scenarios for Hyde’s *The Nativity* (*Dráma Breithe Chríosta*, 1902) and a “Fearful Dream”, again in collaboration with Yeats, once more showing just how collaborative these plays were.²⁸ There was probably collaboration in the translation too: one account has Hyde reading *An Naomh ar Iarraidh* aloud at Coole, “translating it back into English as he went along”.²⁹ If Hyde was already presenting his own English version in this way, before Gregory produced her own translation, this indicates yet another aspect to the collaboration process between the two, one that may have been repeated across other plays.³⁰ While translation manuscripts show Gregory gaining distance from Hyde’s text, retrospective accounts of the composition process show that the lines of influence in this collaborative team were multidirectional, and that they shifted over time.

We again see Gregory’s budding authorial independence in her translation manuscripts of *The Lost Saint*. The saint of the title is yet another unassuming Old Man, who takes care of menial tasks around the school. While the teacher and students go out, he helps the failing pupil Conall to remember a poem attributed to Saint Aongus Céile Dé. When the others come back, Conall recites the entire poem to his dumfounded teacher, who then discovers that the Old Man is none other than the saint himself. Here again, Gregory’s drafts move away from word-for-word translation of Hyde’s versions. While she first translated “béile” as the general “meal”, her typescript introduces the more specific “dinner”.³¹ The fairly literal translation of a talented student speaking bravely before his lesson, “there is no fear on myself” (for “níl eagla orm-sa”), is

²⁷Dunleavy and Dunleavy, *Douglas Hyde*, 223. Trans. in Dunleavy and Dunleavy. Emphasis added.

²⁸As James Pethica points out, this “Fearful Dream” was likely an early title for Hyde’s play *Pleusgadh na Bulgóide; or The Bursting of the Bubble* (1903). *Lady Gregory’s Diaries*, 312n14. Though it is commonly assumed that Gregory is responsible for the English-language sections of this bilingual text, Liam Mac Mathúna makes a convincing case that the translator was Hyde himself. See Mac Mathúna, “Na ról a bhí ag an gCraoibhín Aoibhinn”.

²⁹Gregory qtd in Murphy, “Dear John Quinn”, 125.

³⁰For instance, Gregory often leaves question marks in her translations when having difficulty with an Irish word. Given their close working relationship and his constant encouragement of her Irish-language learning, it is possible that Hyde helped her with such translational difficulties. On the topic of Gregory’s proficiency in Irish, Maureen Murphy notes her difficulties with the spoken language while taking Irish classes at the turn of the century. Murphy, “Gregory and the Gaelic League”, 146–7. There are errors in her translations, as when she translates “ceól na bhárr” [excellent music] as “music on their roof” in *The Tinker and the Sheeog*. Hyde, *Selected Plays*, 66–7. With many thanks to Cian O’Cionnhaolaidh for his insights on this.

³¹Typescript, with translator’s ms. corrections, Berg Collection, 01r. Henceforth referenced as LSTS in the text. See *SP* 108–9; *PD* 236–7.

changed to “for myself” for the published text (LSTS 01r; *SP* 108–9; *PD* 236). Likewise, when the Old Man tells the teacher to trust in God’s grace, “ní chuimhnímid ar na neithe do chailleamar” [we do not think on the things we have lost] (*SP* 114) becomes “he does not think on the thing we are without” (LSTS 05r; *SP* 115; *PD* 241), the final verb changing as well as the subject of the phrase. Having said this, there are also instances of more direct translation, as in the teacher’s angry words to his forgetful student: “O mo náire thu!” [“Oh, my shame you are!”] (*SP* 110–11; *PD* 239) or when “as so amach” becomes “from this out” (*SP* 116–17; *PD* 243). But Gregory is not averse to reshaping her English equivalent, as when the line “tá an leanbh sin go ro mhall ag foghlaim” is reduced to “that child is half-witted” (LSTS 04r; *SP* 114–15; *PD* 241). The above evidence shows that Gregory draws strategically on word-for-word translation, but is not afraid to go her own way when it comes to phrasing the dialogue of plays she initially structured.

With preliminary scenarios, collaboration in translation and some forceful encouragement in getting the work written, translation was by no means a straightforward process in Hyde and Gregory’s creative partnership. This corresponds with the complexity of other, less successful collaborations in the national theatre movement. When Yeats was working with George Moore on their version of *Diarmuid and Grania*, it was suggested “that Moore should write the play in French, that Lady Gregory should translate it into English, that Taidgh O’Donoghue should render it into Irish and Lady Gregory translate it back again into English; after which Yeats was to put style upon it”.³² Though the initial texts were not in French, Gregory’s collaborations with Hyde on *The Marriage* and *The Lost Saint* were just as complex. With Gregory’s input at both ends of the writing process, these plays are truly collaborative, but in spite of this, they are not included in Ann Saddlemyer’s edited volume of the author’s collaborations and translations. From a historical perspective, this is understandable, as we tend to grant authorship to the first published author of a playtext. But, given the interwoven nature of these plays’ geneses, there is a strong case for them to be included in any future edition of Gregory’s works. Likewise, I would question the decision to omit *Teach na mBocht* from Hyde’s *Selected Plays* on the grounds that its English version is an “adaptation[...] rather than [a] translation[...]”.³³ This is true of *The Workhouse Ward*, but not *The Poorhouse*. As we shall now see, both translation and adaptation were involved in this work of deeply interwoven authorship.

From *Teach na mBocht* to *The Workhouse Ward*

What would eventually become *The Workhouse Ward* was just as collaborative in nature as Gregory and Hyde’s earlier plays. In Gregory’s account, the play again had a highly developed scenario before she gave it to Hyde to compose in Irish as *Teach na mBocht*. This preliminary plan was transcribed and published in her 1913 autobiography, *Our Irish Theatre*, where it takes up no fewer than four pages.³⁴ The scenario features all

³²Lyons, “Moore and Martyn”, 17.

³³Dunleavy and Dunleavy, “Introduction”, 22.

³⁴The typescript, corrected in pen and pencil and entitled “Scenario for Hyde” in pencil, matches very closely the text Gregory uses in *Our Irish Theatre*, with only very minor changes made for the published version. Typescript with the author’s ms. corrections, Berg Collection.

the main details of the plot: two elderly men quarrel in their workhouse beds (Colm and Pádraig in *Teach na mBocht*; Colum and Paudeen in *The Poorhouse*; Mike McNerney and Michael Miskell in *The Workhouse Ward*);³⁵ Colm/Colum/Mike receives an offer from his recently widowed sister (Cáit/Kate/Honor) to come and live with her on a farm; he then declines that offer when she refuses to also take his quarrelsome workhouse companion. While, as we have seen above, Gregory created scenarios with Yeats in the knowledge they would be handed over to Hyde for him to write plays in Irish, she was not always enthusiastic about doing so. On this occasion, she recalls, “I intended to write the full dialogue myself, but Mr. Yeats thought a new Gaelic play more useful for the moment, and rather sadly I laid that part of the work upon Dr. Hyde”.³⁶ The above reminiscence suggests the decisive role that Yeats played in shaping Hyde and Gregory’s collaboration. Again, note the sidelining of the female author – this time by her colleague – something which is well worth bearing in mind when analysing the continued evolution of the play.

Published in 1903, her translation, *The Poorhouse*, came near the beginning of Gregory’s playwriting career. Though the manuscript draft of this translation could not be found during my research, an examination of the published texts shows Gregory following the pattern established in the analysis of the plays above, initially making fairly literal translations of Hyde’s play, with “ar deargmheisce” translated as “red drunk” (*DTh* 216; *CP4* 297) and Irish syntactical structures again mirrored in the English. There is evidence of Gregory’s playwriting nous even at this early stage, however, leaving “a little space” between the two beds in the opening stage directions (*CP4* 295) – rather than the more specific “cúig slata” [five yards] of Hyde’s original (*DTh* 213) – so that each group of players could decide for themselves on the precise setup in light of the given stage dimensions. A typescript held in the Berg Collection also shows that there were some limits to direct translation. In an early exchange with the Matron, Colm complains that if his heart was pulled out, scrubbed and put back again, “I would have some ease”, the addition of the determiner “some” qualifying the Irish phrase “go mbeadh socracht agam” (*DTh* 213).³⁷ However, as a whole, the translation published in *Samhain* is close to the Irish-language version, again reflecting Gregory’s proximity to Hyde at this early stage in her career.

Five years later, Gregory had become the most popular Abbey Theatre playwright, achieving success with plays such as *Spreading the News* (staged 1904), *Hyacinth Halvey* (staged 1906), *The Gaol Gate* (staged 1906), *The Jackdaw* (staged 1907) and *The Rising of the Moon* (premiered 1904; staged at the Abbey 1907). In his account of collaborating with Gregory on *Where There is Nothing* (published 1903), which they rewrote as *The Unicorn from the Stars* in 1907, Yeats recalls a marked shift in Gregory’s playwriting skills in these intervening years:

I wrote in 1902, with the help of Lady Gregory and another friend, a play called *Where There Is Nothing* [...]. [In 1907,] I asked Lady Gregory to help me turn my old plot into *The*

³⁵I follow the text of *Teach na mBocht* in *Drámaí Thús na hAthbheochana*, 211–22. Henceforth referenced as *DTh* in the text.

³⁶Gregory, *Our Irish Theatre*, 89.

³⁷Typescript of play with Lady Gregory’s ms. corrections, Berg Collection, 01r. This typescript contains instructions for the printer, so seems to have come late in the translation process, but there were further changes made before publication which suggest authorial involvement. Subsequently referenced as PTS in the text.

Unicorn from the Stars. I began to dictate, but since I had last worked with her, her mastery of the stage and her knowledge of dialect had so increased that my imagination could not go neck to neck with hers.³⁸

It was not every day that W. B. Yeats admitted to being second-best in powers of the imagination. However, his statement needs to be seen in the light of Gregory's stage successes, which made her "the best 'draw' of the lot of you", as Yeats was bluntly informed by Abbey benefactor Annie Horniman in 1906.³⁹ This included Hyde, Synge and all the other Abbey playwrights. Gregory herself says of the adaptation of *The Workhouse Ward*: "I had more skill by that time" with regards to playwriting, something a frequent collaborator such as Yeats was well-placed to judge.⁴⁰ When considering how Gregory elbowed her way back into the composition process of *The Poorhouse* by re-writing it as *The Workhouse Ward*, it is important to bear this increased skill in mind.

When Gregory came to re-write the play, she made it her own. By setting the adaptation in "*Cloon Workhouse*" (CPI 97), she relocated the action to the imaginary village used throughout her oeuvre, leaving us in no doubt that we are now in her theatrical world. Galway placenames such as Skehanagh, Lisheen Crannagh, Newtown Lynch and Duras aid this, constructing an offstage world linked to the area in which Gregory lived and was associated with in the public imagination.⁴¹ The immediate impulse for the adaptation may have been the fact that an English-language production of *The Poorhouse* in 1907 "wasn't entirely successful", with the *Irish Independent* declaring that it was "hardly worth the while of an experienced writer for the stage putting before the public".⁴² The *Independent* listed both writers as co-authors, a tactic explained in Gregory's note for a 1906 edition of the play:

Dr. Douglas Hyde and I wrote *The Poorhouse* together, I giving in plot what he gave back in dialogue. I would not have my name put with his then, as I thought the play would be more acceptable to Irish speakers without even the ancestry of a scenario in the "Bearla" [*sic*].

But now we find that players in English in their turn think we should wrong what was created in Gaelic by playing it in translation; so we have put both our names to the little play with the object rather than the hope of commending it to both sides.⁴³

Gregory is incorrect: her name *does* appear alongside Hyde's in her 1903 translation published in *Samhain*, albeit as translator rather than co-author.⁴⁴ But her note outlines the aim

³⁸Yeats, *Variorum Plays*, 713. Dates of play stagings and compositions taken from CP4 and Kelly, *Yeats Chronology*, 112–13. Gregory too remembers an anonymous third person being involved in this revision process, whom Ann Saddlemyer identifies as Hyde. Saddlemyer, *In Defence*, 17. See Gregory, *Our Irish Theatre*, 80. For a more detailed account of Gregory and Yeats's collaboration, which sets this acknowledgement within a broader pattern of Yeats downplaying Gregory's role as collaborator, see Pethica, "Patronage and Creative Exchange". See also Foster, *The Apprentice Mage*, 267–70.

³⁹Horniman to Yeats, 26 November 1906, qtd in Saddlemyer, *In Defence*, 35. For a statistical account of Gregory's dominance over Yeats and Synge with regard to staged plays in the Abbey between 1904 and 1932, see Pilz, "Return to the People", 4–5.

⁴⁰Gregory, *Our Irish Theatre*, 89–90. *The Workhouse Ward* premiered on 20 April 1908. *Abbey Archive*, https://www.abbeytheatre.ie/archives/production_detail/287/.

⁴¹The manuscript shows Gregory paying particular care to placenames, striking out many to replace them with versions that appear in the published text. Holograph of play, Berg Collection.

⁴²Murphy, "Gregory and the Gaelic League", 154; "New Play by Dr. Hyde", 4.

⁴³Gregory, *Spreading the News*, 48.

⁴⁴Hyde, *The Poorhouse*, 19. In newspaper reports from 1908, *The Workhouse Ward* is typically referred to as Lady Gregory's play in headlines and advertisement, with an account of its co-authorship appearing in accompanying articles. *The Poorhouse* is described as a co-authored piece in an *Irish Independent* article from 4 April 1907. "New Play by Dr. Hyde", 4.

– however undiplomatically expressed – of reconciling Irish- and English-speaking theatre practitioners at a time when different factions of the national theatre movement were under huge strain.⁴⁵ Whatever about this ambition, *The Poorhouse* itself had a very short run (of only three performances), and Gregory soon took the opportunity to rewrite the play.⁴⁶ While, in her memoir, she was careful to note that this was done “with Dr. Hyde’s full leave”, the setting of the adapted play is all Gregory.⁴⁷

“The talk”: from theatrical tool to offstage gossip

In re-writing the play, Gregory cut the offstage audience of other inmates who comment on the two men’s quarrel and substantially added to the dialogue. One such passage added to *The Workhouse Ward* has Michael Miskell rejecting his departing companion’s offer of tobacco as compensation for the impending loss of company:

Ah, what signifies tobacco? All that I am craving is the talk. There to be no one at all to say out to whatever thought might be rising in my innate mind! To be lying here and no conversible person in it would be the abomination of misery!⁴⁸

Miskell is not the first Gregory character to thematise the importance of talk. For Saddlemyer, “the talk’ is all” for those who populate her comic plays, with the threat of being deprived of social contact the greatest this critic can imagine for Gregory’s characters.⁴⁹ However, there is also evidence of a darker side to such speech, rumour and gossip across the playwright’s oeuvre. In *The Travelling Man*, the Mother recalls being driven out of the house where she worked as a serving girl “because of some things that were said against me” (CP3 21). In *The Full Moon*, the reluctant hero Hyacinth Halvey says he would leave town “if it wasn’t for the talk the neighbours would be making” (CP3 38). Gregory’s first play staged at the Abbey was *Spreading the News*, in which village gossip leads to a wrongful arrest for a murder that never happened (CP1 15–29). In *The Gaol Gate*, two women mourn outside a prison not only the death of an imprisoned young man, but the malicious gossip that threatens to ruin his posthumous reputation (CP2 5–6). And at least two Gregory characters complain of there being “too much talk”, one in an asylum, the other in a rural village.⁵⁰ In these instances, talk is a malignant force, but *The Workhouse Ward* foregrounds the importance of “the talk” as the glue that constitutes social networks, as well as – if we are to believe Michael’s pleading – something that holds together the very agents that constitute these networks. While Yeats would high-handedly dismiss Gregory’s writing as the work of an author belonging to a world “that is merely social”, again suggesting a gendered dismissal of her theatrical craft, “the talk” is the engine of her plays, and no doubt played a part in making them so popular.⁵¹

The form of dialogue deployed in *The Workhouse Ward* had a specific source. Éadaoin Ní Mhuirheartaigh traces the “talk” of this play to the *agallamh beirte*, a form of

⁴⁵See Foster, *The Apprentice Mage*, 334–58.

⁴⁶Abbey Archive, <https://www.abbeytheatre.ie/archives/search/plays/The%20Poorhouse/>.

⁴⁷Gregory, *Our Irish Theatre*, 89.

⁴⁸Gregory, *Comedies*, 102. Further references to all four volumes of *The Collected Plays* as CP in the text.

⁴⁹Saddlemyer, *In Defence*, 26; see also Saddlemyer, “Foreword” to CP1, ix.

⁵⁰Mrs Fallon in *Hyacinth Halvey* tells the gossiping villagers: “It is too much talk the whole of you have” (CP1 22). In *The Full Moon*, Cracked Mary describes the asylum: “Too much of talk and of noise there was in it” (CP3 36).

⁵¹Qtd in Pethica, “Patronage and Creative Exchange”, 184.

performed Irish-language poetry recited by two speakers.⁵² Though Gregory's drama is not in verse, and though her dialogue is unrhymed, the to-and-fro of the two-handed dialogue evokes a form which she was familiar with from Gaelic League events.⁵³ What is more, the insults exchanged evoke the frequently comic tone of the *agallamh*. Of the thirty-nine paragraphs of dialogue exchanged between Pádraig and Colm in *Teach na mBocht*, only Pádraig's plea for Colm to remain with him in the workhouse lacks the bite of insult or threat of physical violence (*DTh* 218).

As Anthony Roche has noted, Pádraig's accusation that Colm was educated at a "Souper school" (*CP4* 296) stands as an Anglicism in Hyde's Irish text: "ní chuig scoil na *Soupers* a bhínn ag dul ag fáil mo chuid foghlama mar thusa" (*DTh* 215).⁵⁴ Indeed, this is part of a broader pattern whereby terms associated with state institutions remain in English in *Teach na mBocht* – "barracks" and "Peelers" being two other examples (*DTh* 216). Writing on the widespread use of English loanwords in turn-of-the-century Irish, Patrick Dinneen commented: "The lexicographer may deplore the introduction of loan words, but he is bound to recognise their existence". He goes on:

Every tongue borrows from other tongues, and it is a sign of health and vigour when a language can assimilate a crop of foreign words and reduce them to subjection by the rigorous application of its own syntax and of its own inflexional forms.⁵⁵

As shown in Gregory's use of "pilér" as part of her description of the Punch-and-Judy show, her collaboration with Hyde took place right in the midst of such linguistic borrowing and remoulding, into which Dinneen's dictionary – commissioned by Hyde's Irish Texts Society – attempted to provide a standardised reference point.⁵⁶ Of course, playwrights have freer linguistic rein than lexicographers, so it is noteworthy that both *The Poorhouse* and *Teach na mBocht* feature *unassimilated* loanwords, marked in italics in the published texts and carefully underlined on Gregory's translator's typescript. In *The Poorhouse* these Gaelicisms are the Irish-language insults "Rogaire" [rouge] and "sprealairé" (*CP4* 296, 298, 301), the latter translated in Dinneen's 1904 dictionary as a variant form of "breallaire": "a giddy, thoughtless fellow, a poltroon".

"Souper" would have been a particularly sensitive insult for Gregory in the period she was working on *The Workhouse Ward*, and the surrounding circumstances may explain why this term of abuse does not appear in her rewritten play. In January 1907, yet another controversy erupted around Synge's work, with riots taking place during the opening run of *The Playboy of the Western World*, which ignited tensions in Gort. As we have seen above, Gregory used Coole Park to stage entertainment for children from the local workhouse. Following what was seen by some as her fellow Abbey director's assault on Irish national character, Gregory was banned from hosting these children at her home. On 17 August 1907, the dispute rumbled on, as Gregory told John Quinn:

⁵²Ní Mhuirheartaigh, "Drámaíocht Dhúchasach?".

⁵³*Ibid.*, 40.

⁵⁴Roche, "Re-working *The Workhouse Ward*", 180.

⁵⁵Dinneen, "Editor's Preface", xi.

⁵⁶In this case, Gregory had personal ties to the linguistic source: the English term "peeler" derives from the association of the Irish constabulary with Prime Minister Robert Peel, a key figure in her late husband William's political career (*OED*). The link was still alive as late as February 1899, when she approached Peel's son to enquire about arranging a clerkship in the House of Commons for her own son, Robert. Hill, "Finding a Voice", 32.

I am still suffering from the Playboy run. [...] The embargo has not been taken off the work-house children, & a feeling is being nourished against me by a Sinn Féin or G[aelic] L[eague] curate in Gort that I am not to be trusted even that I am “souperizing”!⁵⁷

To understand the damage of such anti-Gregory gossip, we need to understand the history of the term “souper”. David W. Miller outlines its history: “In popular Catholic memory, proselytising the starving during the Famine is called ‘souperism’, from the term ‘souper’ that was applied to a starving Catholic who was converted to Protestantism”. Miller traces localised use of the term in Dingle, Co. Kerry “before the 1845 potato crop failure” that triggered the Famine. However, it was in the 1850s that the term became widespread in newspapers like the *Freeman’s Journal*.⁵⁸ In 1907, the term “souper” had contemporary resonance for a Protestant landowner seeking to maintain positive relations with her predominantly Catholic tenant farmers.⁵⁹ Like many of her tenants, Gregory was intimately aware of the legacy of the Famine, though from a very different perspective to theirs: her late husband William Gregory, MP had created the infamous Gregory Clause in the Poor Law Bill of 1847, which limited relief to those holding no more than a quarter of an acre.⁶⁰ Since this meant that their families were then also ineligible for relief, tenant farmers were presented with a terrible choice: “To save himself and his family from starvation a cottier would have to relinquish his plot”.⁶¹ In introducing this clause, William Gregory created a dark legacy which successive instances of local charity would never shake off. Such was the backdrop to Lady Gregory’s being labelled a “souper” in local gossip against her.⁶²

In Gregory’s diaries, a frequently stated priority is to carefully negotiate the changing relationships of landlord and tenant brought about by the turn-of-the-century Land Acts so that her son Robert can peacefully inherit her estate. Hence, a public dispute like this – at a time when relations were already strained – was particularly threatening. Five years earlier, however, Gregory had been happy to have this term included in the original text.⁶³ The “souper” insult is part of her preliminary sketch for *Teach na mBocht*, where she emphasises the taboo nature of souperism in edits to her typescript: “Other old man remembers time the other ^{was suspected of going} to souper school” (PTS 01r). With the negative connotations associated with souperism, and her late husband’s role in the mass suffering brought about by the Famine, she may not have wished to broach the subject in *The Workhouse Ward* at a point where she herself was being accused of “souperizing”.⁶⁴ In this instance, “the talk” that circulated in Gort against Gregory following the *Playboy* riots may have led to the removal of this insult.

⁵⁷Qtd in Hill, *Lady Gregory*, 210. Square brackets in Hill. The ban was enforced by Fr Fahey, who had opened the Kiltartan Gaelic League branch with Hyde (see above).

⁵⁸Miller, “Soup and Providence”, 65–6; emphasis in original.

⁵⁹For more on the contemporary weight of the term “souper”, via an analysis of the controversy surrounding the portrayal of souperism in Dinneen’s 1901 play *Creideamh agus Gorta*, see Ní Mhuircheartaigh, “Réamhrá”, 23–5.

⁶⁰Hill, *Lady Gregory*, 21.

⁶¹Jenkins, *William Gregory*, 74–5.

⁶²Gregory would later be furious with George Moore when he described her and her sister as “ardent soul-gatherers” in *The English Review*. Moore, “Yeats, Lady Gregory, and Synge”, 175. See Frazier, *George Moore*, 390–1. With many thanks to Nicholas Grene for bringing this to my attention.

⁶³It also turns up in her 1904 play *Spreading the News* (CP1 21).

⁶⁴Gregory also cuts a reference to what appears to be land agitation by omitting the story of Colum burning down the barn of Seaghan Ban (see CP4 297; DTh 215).

Workhouse shadows

As well as influencing the vocabulary of the play, the Famine also haunts *The Workhouse Ward* through its being set in an institution associated with poor relief. There are language dynamics at play here too. Though Irish was “already in rapid retreat before 1845”, the Famine “played its part” in the language’s decline by disproportionately affecting rural areas where it was most widely spoken.⁶⁵ More to the point, the workhouse was where Gregory collected much of her Irish-language folklore, usually assisted by a translator.⁶⁶ Gregory and her theatre collaborators drew much of their creative material from rural, Irish-speaking districts, be it language, setting or sometimes even pieces of clothing.⁶⁷ *Teach na mBocht / The Poorhouse / The Workhouse Ward* can be seen as an institutional offshoot of the cottage-kitchen style that dominated the early national theatre movement,⁶⁸ with the sister’s promise of rural domestic bliss – “A wide lovely house I have; a few acres of grass land” (CP1 101) – forming an alluring contrast to the bedbound conflict we see onstage. However, box-set domesticity was by no means the only spatial form in Gregory’s plays. As Patrick Lonergan has pointed out, she often set her plays outdoors, in spaces quite unlike the frequently used cottage-kitchen setup.⁶⁹ Given this versatility, why use a workhouse for this play? If theatre spaces are “almost invariably haunted in one way or another”, then Gregory’s choice of setting evokes very particular, very unsettling ghosts.⁷⁰

A biographical reading could, with some justification, claim Gregory’s source for the scenario as inspiration for the stage setting: she heard the story in Gort Workhouse about a quarrelling couple, so the workhouse was an obvious place to set the play.⁷¹ However, the workhouse in the early national theatre was by no means a neutral space; it was a powerful agent of meaning, freighted by the “taint” of material poverty and its association with Famine relief.⁷² Gort Workhouse had a particularly grim history of overcrowding and mass burial during this period, which led to the local Board of Guardians being convicted of negligence in 1848.⁷³ Lady Gregory would have been fully aware of its history, with her husband having chaired the Board of Guardians in the 1850s.⁷⁴ With this in mind, it is no surprise that the social “taint” of the workhouse is evident across her dramatic writing: her stage characters repeatedly describe the institution in negative terms, from Bartley Fallon’s fear of dying if he is sent there in *The Full Moon* (CP3 44–5) to Darby’s shame at having been “partly reared in the workhouse” in *The Bogie Men* (CP1 113).⁷⁵

In *Teach na mBocht / The Poorhouse*, Hyde and Gregory play on these negative associations in Cáit’s opening words to Colm: “Ara, a Choilm, a chroí, nach bocht an áit a

⁶⁵Ó Gráda, *Great Irish Famine*, 75.

⁶⁶See Gregory, *Poets and Dreamers*, 2nd ed., 130.

⁶⁷Morash and Richards, *Mapping Irish Theatre*, 39.

⁶⁸*Ibid.*, 36.

⁶⁹Lonergan, *Theatre Revivals for the Anthropocene*, 57–8.

⁷⁰Carlson, *Haunted Stage*, 132.

⁷¹Gregory, *Our Irish Theatre*, 86.

⁷²See Little, “Home, the Asylum, and the Workhouse”; Lucey, “These Schemes”, 58, 61.

⁷³Jenkins, *William Gregory*, 91–3.

⁷⁴*Ibid.*, 109. Lady Gregory even tried to introduce cottage industries at the workhouse, but this was blocked by Fr Fahey. Rempfort, *Lady Gregory*, 89.

⁷⁵The stigma of the workhouse is also mentioned in *The Jackdaw* (CP1 72–3, 89), *McDonough’s Wife* (CP2 117), *The Image* (CP2 163) and *Dave* (CP3 350–1, 355).

bhfeicim thú” (*DTh* 217) [“Aurah, Colum, achree! Isn’t it a poor place that I see you?”] (*CP4* 298). Indeed, the comic nature of Colum’s choice to stay in the workhouse is underpinned by the audience assumption that it is an awful place to live – as playgoers, we bring our own knowledge of the ghosts haunting a stage setting to any given production. His justification of this choice highlights public “talk” about the workhouse “taint”, telling his sister that the institution is “not as bad you know *as they say*” (*CP4* 300; emphasis added). However, it is important to note that the staged image of life in the workhouse is comfortable, not carceral: the action opens with the Matron asking Colm if he would like some milk, and there is no sign of the institutional mistreatment that other Gregory characters complain about and fear. In *The Workhouse Ward*, Gregory again has the visiting sister reference the social stigma associated with the institution: “It is no credit to me a brother of my own to be in this place at all” (*CPI* 101).⁷⁶ But, in *Teach na mBocht / The Poorhouse*, the workhouse is remarkable insofar as it is – in contrast to its representation in the dialogue of this and other Gregory plays – a fairly neutral backdrop to the comic action. Likewise, in the later rewrite, the workhouse “taint” is not the dominant aspect of the stage space. In *The Workhouse Ward*, all interactions with other inmates and staff members are cut, leaving the focus more directly on “the talk” of the two men.⁷⁷ Her edits also render the spatial politics of the institution more malleable for those wishing to restage the play, making it a much more neutral spatial agent than one might expect. Ultimately, staging as comedy an institution associated with Ireland’s greatest tragedy creates deeply unsettling theatrical effects.

Conclusion

No collaboration can be fully reconstructed. However, by “letting the archives speak” and following the material traces of Gregory and Hyde’s creative partnership, we can get a deeper understanding of how their network worked.⁷⁸ In her article on the potential benefits of Actor–Network Theory for translation studies, Buzelin calls for a “genesis of literary translations” that takes into account “strategies, negotiations, struggles, conflicts – but also alliances” involved in bilingual literary production.⁷⁹ Drawing on the translation manuscripts in the Berg Collection helps to provide such insight into Hyde’s and Gregory’s creative strategies. An analysis of the different textual versions of this play further erodes the “battle of two civilizations” model that P. J. Mathews has critiqued as being overly influential in studies of the Revival.⁸⁰ Instead, what we see is the bilingual nature of their collaboration, with Gaelicisms and Anglicisms cross-pollinating different versions, and each author involved in shaping English and Irish versions of each other’s texts.

Such genetic research can also extend our notion of authorship. Previous scholarship has led us to reconsider the authorship of revivalist plays once considered the work of a single writer, the best-known example being the belated inclusion of Gregory as co-

⁷⁶This stigma is already evident in Gregory’s scenario, where the sister “doesn’t [*sic*] like to think of her brother being in the workhouse” (PTS 01r).

⁷⁷Ní Mhuircheartaigh, “Drámaíocht Dhúchasach?”, 40.

⁷⁸Houlihan, *Theatre and Archival Memory*, 249.

⁷⁹Buzelin, “Unexpected Allies”, 208.

⁸⁰Mathews, *Revival*.

author, with Yeats, of *Cathleen ni Houlihan*. What I have suggested above is a further reconsideration of authorial activity in collaboratively composed texts, particularly when it comes to future editions of Gregory's and Hyde's works. When there are new editions of these playwrights' dramas, it would be worth including all plays in which they had a significant creative input. Furthermore, since we know that there were multiple hands at work on many of the plays that emerged from the Coole "workshop", this argument may be relevant for other cases within the Irish Revival, and possibly beyond it as well.

Alongside these alliances, "struggles" and "conflicts" existed too, with Gregory often finding herself sidelined as a female author in a male-dominated network, even writing herself out of her retrospective account of her collaborations with Hyde. She was clearly put out to be told she should hand a play over to Hyde for composition in Irish. However, having built up the strongest stage record of any Abbey playwright, five years later she reclaimed the text by adapting it as *The Workhouse Ward*. The conflict within the play in the form of vituperative "talk" found its counterpart in the offstage world around Gort, and, knowing what we know about the difficulties women have faced in the Irish cultural sphere, it is difficult to believe that anti-Gregory gossip in the wake of Synge's *Playboy* did not also have gendered aspects to it.⁸¹

While Gregory faced opposition in Gort following the *Playboy* riots, the 1908 staging of *The Workhouse Ward* firmly established her as the Abbey's leading playwright, with the *Freeman's Journal* calling her "the most prolific" as well as "the healthiest and most attractive" of the Irish National Theatre Society writers.⁸² As we know, this reputation did not last: having been performed almost every year from 1908 until the Second World War, Gregory's *Workhouse Ward* has only had five productions at the Abbey since 1945, only recently to be revived.⁸³ However, O'Leary's extensive list of Irish-language translations of Gregory's work shows that her plays did not fall out of favour in Irish. O'Leary points out that Gregory was the most popular revivalist playwright when it came to translations of her work into that language, indicating that the staged afterlife of Gregory's work has needed the language just as much as the early versions did.⁸⁴ Engaging further with archival materials in both languages promises to tell us more about the collaborations and networks of the Irish Revival, thus deepening our knowledge of the politics of bilingual theatre collaboration.

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⁸¹See Gerardine Meaney, *Gender, Ireland, and Cultural Change*.

⁸²"The Abbey Theatre", *Freeman's Journal*, 21 April 1908, 4.

⁸³*Abbey Archive*, <https://www.abbeytheatre.ie/archives/search/plays/workhouse/>. The Irish Repertory Theatre staged the play in 2020 (<https://irishrep.org/show/2019-2020/lady-g/>).

⁸⁴O'Leary, "What Would Willie Say?", 170–1. There was also nationalist uptake of Gregory's plays, including a staging of *The Rising of the Moon* in Kilmainham Jail by anti-Treaty inmates in 1923. Saunders, *Prison Journal*, 26v. When these prisoners were transferred to the North Dublin Union, they named one of their dormitories there "Workhouse Ward". Matthews, *Dissidents*, 93. Eamon Broy claimed that *The Rising of the Moon* inspired his undercover intelligence work for the IRA following the 1916 Rising, and that Michael Collins considered it "The best play Lady Gregory ever wrote". Pilz, "From Gort to Antarctica", 154–5.

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References

- The Abbey Theatre Archive*, <https://www.abbeytheatre.ie/archives>.
- “The Abbey Theatre”, *Freeman’s Journal*, 21 April 1908, 4.
- “Aenach Tirconail – The Great Irish Festival”, *Freeman’s Journal*, 19 November 1898, 6.
- Buzelin, Hélène. “Translations ‘in the Making’.” In *Constructing a Sociology of Translation*, ed. Michaela Wolf and Alexandra Fukari, 135–69. Amsterdam: John Benjamins, 2007.
- . “Unexpected Allies: How Latour’s Network Theory Could Complement Bourdieusian Analyses in Translation Studies.” *The Translator* 11, no. 2 (2005): 193–218.
- Carlson, Marvin. *The Haunted Stage: The Theatre as Memory Machine*. Ann Arbor: University of Michigan Press, 2011.
- Cordingley, Anthony, and Céline Frigau Manning. “What Is Collaborative Translation?” In *Collaborative Translation: From the Renaissance to the Digital Age*, ed. Anthony Cordingley and Céline Frigau Manning, 1–30. London: Bloomsbury Academic, 2017.
- Cordingley, Anthony, and Chiara Montini. “Genetic Translation Studies: An Emerging Discipline.” *Linguistica Antverpiensia, New Series: Themes in Translation Studies* 14 (2015): 1–18.
- Dinneen, Patrick S. “Editor’s Preface.” In *Foclóir Gaedhilge agus Béarla: An Irish–English Dictionary*, ed. Patrick S. Dinneen, v–xiii. Dublin: M. H. Gill & Son and The Gaelic League; London: David Nutt, 1904.
- Dunleavy, Gareth W. “The Pattern of Three Threads: The Hyde–Gregory Friendship.” In *Lady Gregory, Fifty Years After*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer and Colin Smythe, 131–42. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe; Totowa, NJ: Barnes & Noble Books, 1987.
- Dunleavy, Janet Egleson, and Gareth W. Dunleavy. *Douglas Hyde: A Maker of Modern Ireland*. Berkeley: University of California Press, 1991.
- . “Introduction.” In *Selected Plays of Douglas Hyde*, ed. Gareth W. Dunleavy and Janet Egleson Dunleavy, 7–30. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe; Washington, DC: Catholic University of America Press, 1991.
- Foster, R. F. *The Apprentice Mage, 1865–1914*. Vol. 1 of *W. B. Yeats: A Life*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 1997.
- Frazier, Adrian. *George Moore, 1852–1933*. New Haven: Yale University Press, 2000.
- Gregory, Lady. *The Comedies*. Vol. 1 of *The Collected Plays*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1979.
- . *Cuchulain of Muirthemne: The Story of the Men of the Red Branch of Ulster*. 4th ed. London: John Murray, 1911.
- . *Lady Gregory Collection of Papers, 1873–[1965]* (Bulk 1873–1932). Henry W. and Albert A. Berg Collection of English and American Literature, New York Public Library.
- . *Lady Gregory’s Diaries, 1892–1902*. Ed. James Pethica. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1996.
- . *Our Irish Theatre: A Chapter of Autobiography*. New York: G. P. Putnam’s Sons, 1913.
- . *Poets and Dreamers: Studies & Translations from the Irish*. 2nd ed. Dublin: Hodges, Figgis & Co.; London: John Murray, 1903.
- . *Poets and Dreamers: Studies and Translations from the Irish by Lady Gregory, Including Nine Plays by Douglas Hyde*. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1974.

- . *Spreading the News; The Rising of the Moon, by Lady Gregory. The Poorhouse, by Lady Gregory and Douglas Hyde*. Dublin: Maunsel & Co, 1906.
- . *The Tragedies and Tragic-comedies*. Vol. 2 of *The Collected Plays*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1979.
- . *The Translations and Adaptations of Lady Gregory and Her Collaborations with Douglas Hyde and W. B. Yeats*. Vol. 4 of *The Collected Plays*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1979.
- . *The Wonder and Supernatural Plays*. Vol. 3 of *The Collected Plays*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1979.
- Grene, Nicholas. “Lady Gregory: Patronage, Collaboration, Mythopoeia.” In *The Oxford Handbook of W. B. Yeats*, ed. Lauren Arrington and Matthew Campbell, 58–70. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2023.
- Hill, Judith. “Finding a Voice: Augusta Gregory, Raftery, and Cultural Nationalism, 1899–1900.” *Irish University Review* 34, no. 1 (2004): 21–36.
- . *Lady Gregory: An Irish Life*. Stroud: Sutton Publishing, 2005.
- Hindley, Reg. *The Death of the Irish Language: A Qualified Obituary*. London: Routledge, 1990.
- Houlihan, Barry. *Theatre and Archival Memory: Irish Drama and Marginalised Histories, 1951–1977*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2021.
- Hyde, Douglas. [“An Craoibhín Aoibhinn.”] *Abhráin Grádh Chúige Connacht, or, Love Songs of Connacht*, 4th ed. Vol. 4 of *Songs of Connacht*. Dublin: Gill & Son; London: T. Fisher Unwin, 1905.
- . *The Poorhouse*, trans. Lady Gregory. *Samhain*, ed. W. B. Yeats (September 1903): 19–24.
- . [“An Craoibhín Aoibhinn.”] *Selected Plays of Douglas Hyde, with Translations by Lady Gregory*. Ed. Gareth W. Dunleavy and Janet Egleson Dunleavy. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe; Washington, DC: Catholic University of America Press, 1991.
- Irish Repertory Theatre*, <https://irishrep.org>.
- Jenkins, Brian. *Sir William Gregory of Coole: The Biography of an Anglo-Irishman*. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1986.
- Kelly, John S. *W. B. Yeats Chronology*. Basingstoke: Palgrave Macmillan, 2003.
- Kiberd, Declan. *Synge and the Irish Language*. London: Macmillan, 1979.
- Latour, Bruno. *Reassembling the Social: An Introduction to Actor-Network-Theory*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2005.
- Little, James. “Home, the Asylum, and the Workhouse in The Shadow of the Glen.” *Irish University Review* 46, no. 2 (2016): 260–74.
- London, Bette. *Writing Double: Women’s Literary Partnerships*. Ithaca: Cornell University Press, 1999.
- Lonergan, Patrick. *Theatre Revivals for the Anthropocene*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2023.
- Lucey, Donnacha Seán. “‘These Schemes Will Win for Themselves the Confidence of the People’: Irish Independence, Poor Law Reform and Hospital Provision.” *Medical History* 58, no. 1 (2014): 46–66.
- Lyons, F. S. L. “George Moore and Edward Martyn.” *Hermathena: A Dublin University Review*, no. 98 (1964): 9–32.
- Mac Mathúna, Liam. “Na ról a bhí ag an gCraoibhín Aoibhinn, an Géagán Glas agus ‘G. G.’ i gcumadh *Pleusgadh na Bulgóide; Or the Bursting of the Bubble* (1903).” In *Ó Chleamairí go Ceamaraí: Drámaíocht agus Taibhealaíona na Gaeilge faoi chaibidil*, ed. Éadaoin Ní Mhuircheartaigh, Róisín Ní Ghairbhí, and Pádraig Ó Liatháin, 19–33. Dublin: Cló Léann na Gaeilge, 2021.
- Mathews, P. J. *Revival: The Abbey Theatre, Sinn Féin, The Gaelic League and the Co-operative Movement*. Cork: Cork University Press, 2003.
- Matthews, Ann. *Dissidents: Irish Republican Women, 1922–1941*. Cork: Mercier Press, 2012.
- Meaney, Gerardine. *Gender, Ireland, and Cultural Change: Race, Sex, and Nation*. New York: Routledge, 2010.

- Miller, David W. "Soup and Providence: Varieties of Protestantism and the Great Famine." In *Ireland's Great Famine and Popular Politics*, ed. Enda Delaney and Breandán Mac Suibhne, 59–79. New York: Routledge, 2016.
- Moore, George. "Yeats, Lady Gregory, and Synge." *The English Review* 16 (1914): 167–80.
- Morash, Chris, and Shaun Richards. *Mapping Irish Theatre: Theories of Space and Place*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2016.
- Murphy, Daniel J. "Dear John Quinn." In *Lady Gregory, Fifty Years After*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer and Colin Smythe, 123–30. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe; Totowa, NJ: Barnes & Noble Books, 1987.
- Murphy, Maureen. "Lady Gregory and the Gaelic League." In *Lady Gregory, Fifty Years After*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer and Colin Smythe, 143–62. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe; Totowa, NJ: Barnes & Noble Books, 1987.
- "A New Play by Dr. Hyde: Quadruple Bill at the Abbey", *Irish Independent*, 4 April 1907, 4.
- Ní Mhuircheartaigh, Éadaoin. "Drámaíocht Dhúchasach? An tAgallamh Fileata ar Ardán na hAthbheochana." *Léann: Iris Chumann Léann na Litríochta* 4 (2016): 23–46.
- . "Réamhrá." In *Drámaí Thús na hAthbheochana*, ed. Éadaoin Ní Mhuircheartaigh and Nollaig Mac Congáil, 7–42. Galway: Arlen House, 2008.
- Ní Mhuircheartaigh, Éadaoin, and Nollaig Mac Congáil, eds. *Drámaí Thús na hAthbheochana*. Galway: Arlen House, 2008.
- Ó Conchubhair, Brian. "Twisting in the Wind: Irish-language Stage Theatre, 1884–2014." In *The Oxford Handbook of Modern Irish Theatre*, ed. Nicholas Grene and Chris Morash, 251–68. Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2016.
- Ó Gráda, Cormac. *The Great Irish Famine*. Basingstoke: Macmillan, 1992.
- O'Leary, Philip. "What Would Willie Say?: Lady Gregory and Popular Theatre in Irish", Paper Read at the Lady Gregory Autumn Gathering at Coole Park, September 2010. *Journal of the Galway Archaeological and Historical Society* 63 (2011): 158–80.
- Ó Siadhail, Pádraig. *Stair Dhrámaíocht na Gaeilge: 1900–1970*. Indreabhán: Cló Iar-Chonnachta, 1993.
- Pethica, James. "'Our Kathleen': Yeats's Collaboration with Lady Gregory in the Writing of *Cathleen ni Houlihan*." In *Yeats and Women*, 2nd ed., ed. Deirdre Toomey, 205–22. Basingstoke: Macmillan; New York, St Martin's Press, 1997.
- . "Patronage and Creative Exchange: Yeats, Lady Gregory and the Economy of Indebtedness." In *Yeats and Women*, 2nd ed., ed. Deirdre Toomey, 168–204. Basingstoke: Macmillan; New York: St Martin's Press, 1997.
- Pilz, Anna. "From Gort to Antarctica: Lady Gregory's Audiences and *The Rising of the Moon* (1903)." In *1716–1992*, vol. 1 of *The Golden Thread: Irish Women Playwrights, 1716–2016*, ed. David Clare, Fiona McDonagh, and Justine Nakase, 133–58. Liverpool: Liverpool University Press, 2021.
- . "'The Return to the People': Empire, Class, and Religion in Lady Gregory's Dramatic Works." PhD thesis, University of Liverpool, 2013.
- Remport, Eglantina. *Lady Gregory and Irish National Theatre: Art, Drama, Politics*. Cham: Palgrave Macmillan, 2018.
- Roche, Anthony. "Re-working *The Workhouse Ward*: McDonagh, Beckett, and Gregory." *Irish University Review* 34, no. 1 (2004): 171–84.
- Saddlemyer, Ann. "Foreword." In *Lady Gregory, The Comedies*, vol. 1 of *The Collected Plays*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer, v–x. Gerrards Cross: Colin Smythe, 1979.
- . *In Defence of Lady Gregory, Playwright*. Dublin: Dolmen Press, 1966.
- Saunders, Cecilia. *Prison Journal of Cecilia Saunders*, Trinity College Dublin MS 10056.
- Synge, J. M. *Plays 2*, vol. 4 of *Collected Works*, ed. Ann Saddlemyer. London: Oxford University Press, 1968.
- Yeats, W. B. *The Variorum Edition of the Plays of W. B. Yeats*. Ed. Russell K. Alspach, assisted by Catharine C. Alspach. Basingstoke: Macmillan, 1989.